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Digital Teacher Competence

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ABSTRACT

The acquisition and updating of digital teacher competence is a requirement in the knowledge society. There are many possibilities offered by ICT for teacher training. A typology of web resources is presented based on information (general video channels, ...), collaboration (blog, wiki, ...) and learning (ePortfolio, PLE, educational video channels, ...) categories, that can help to plan the teaching practice. Several proposals have been made to systematize the levels of acquisition of digital teacher competences: ICT Competency Standards for Teachers (ICT-CST) (UNESCO, 2008), and ICT Competencies' Pentagon (MEN, 2013). In addition, teachers have at their disposal a variety of technopedagogical models for the technology integration in educational contexts, like for example: Technical, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge Model (TPACK) (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), and Substitution, Augmentation, Modification and Redefinition Model (SAMR) (Puentedura, 2014). Finally, some strategies with ICT Resources are proposed to be implemented in distance learning contexts.

INTRODUCTION

Digital competence has been defined by Ala-Mutka (2011, p. 3) as the “confident, critical and creative use of ICT to achieve goals related to work, employability, learning, leisure, inclusion and/or participation in society”. The digital competence can be developed through five underlying concepts (Cobo, 2009, p. 20): *E-awareness* (user's awareness of ICT and appreciation of the relevance of these ICT in the information based society), *Technological literacy* (critical use of electronic media for study, work, leisure and communication), *Informational literacy* (ability to understand, assess and interpret information from all kinds of sources), *Digital literacy* (proficiency to build new knowledge, based on the strategic employment of ICT for search, access, management, creation and communication) and *Media literacy* (understanding how the traditional mass media and the digital media are merging).

Some of the skills related to digital literacy (Cobo, 2009, p. 22) are: *definition* (using ICT tools to search, find, identify and recognize the information need); *access* (knowing how to collect and/or retrieve information in digital environments and the ability to develop a search strategy to locate information from different sources); *management* (organizing information into one or more classification schemes); *creation* (generating new information and knowledge by adapting, designing, editing, inventing, or representing information in ICT environments) and *communication* (conveying information and knowledge to various individuals and/or groups).

Digital teacher competence is defined throughout the domain of the different areas: Information processing, Communication, Content creation, Problem solving and Security (Ferrari, 2013, and Vuorikari, Punie, Carretero & Van den Brande, 2016) [Figure 1].

Figure 1: Digital Competences for Teachers (based on Vuorikari et al, 2016)

The different components of the digital teacher competence can be developed through an online course on Moodle platform created under the DigiComp project offering the opportunity to complete all the tasks in the five competences to obtain a certificate.

After that select with which competence you would like to start. Complete all the tasks in the five competences and submit and grade your final coursework and earn your DIGICOMP certificate.

Some items to self-assessment of the digital teacher competence for a proficient user are presented as follows [Table 1].

Table 1: Digital competences - Self-assessment grid - Proficient user (item examples)

Competence area	Description
Information processing	I can assess the validity and credibility of information using a range of criteria. I can save information found on the internet in different formats. I can use cloud information storage services.
Communication	I actively use a wide range of communication tools (e-mail, chat, SMS, instant messaging, blogs, micro-blogs, social networks) for online communication. I actively participate in online spaces and use several online services (e.g. public services, e-banking, online shopping). I can use advanced features of communication tools (e.g. video conferencing, data sharing, application sharing).
Content creation	I can produce or modify complex, multimedia content in different formats, using a variety of digital platforms, tools and environments. I can use advanced formatting functions of different tools (e.g. merging documents of different formats, using advanced formulas, macros). I know how to apply licenses and copyrights.
Problem solving	I am aware of new technological developments. I understand how new tools work. I frequently update my digital skills.
Safety	I frequently check the security configuration and systems of my devices and/or of the applications I use. I can configure or modify the firewall and security settings of my digital devices. I can apply filters to spam e-mails. I make reasonable use of information and communication technology.

Source : <http://europass.cedefop.europa.eu/resources/digital-competences>

The acquisition and updating of digital teacher competence is a requirement in the knowledge society. Students for education major consider the intensive use of digital technologies as one of the necessary skills for them and their teachers (Campos & Solano, 2017).

The ICT Competences and Standards Model from the pedagogical dimension (Valencia et al, 2016) presents three levels of appropriation of ICT: Integration, Re-orientation and Evolution, which are broken down into three elements: Know, Use and Transform. This model proposes a training route that consists on five phases: (1) Assessment of the level of appropriation of ICT in educational practices, (2) Reflection and instruction in the use of ICT for the promotion of (3) Guided use of ICT-supported educational practices; (4) Review of the results of the implementation of ICT-supported educational practice; and (5) Systematization of educational practices supported by successful ICT.

Different typologies, standards, and models for digital teacher competence has been select to allow teachers to design and evaluate didactic strategies according to their educational context. These theoretical proposals orient the teachers in the approach from different levels, from educational policies, through the guidelines for ICT initial and continuing training plans.

1. WEB RESOURCES TYPOLOGY

There are many possibilities offered by ICT for teacher training. We outline a proposal for classifying web resources on information, collaboration and learning, although in practice we will find educational hybrid configurations [Figure 2].

Figure 2: Web resources typology (Cacheiro, 2011)

This classification enables instructional designers to develop exemplifications, while the same resource can be used for different purposes and therefore can be included in more than one category.

1.1. Web Information Resources

Web resources provide additional information to address a topic from basic to advanced levels. Some Web Information Resources include: webgraphy, virtual encyclopedias, online databases, or web 2.0 tools. Web 2.0 tools enable the user to browse, create and share documents containing information on a subject through resources in various formats, including texts, videos, and graphic presentations.

Some tools that facilitate this task are social bookmarks such as del.icio.us, that allow the creation and sharing of resources indexed by labels or tags. Video repositories such as YouTube, allow the upload of videos or audio recordings on various topics. Graphic presentations as prezi, which facilitates the consultation of presentations of different subjects of congresses or workshops.

1.2. Web Collaboration Resources

Web resources for collaboration offer users the opportunity to participate in professional networks and co-create resources. Collaborative work allows the assessment of existing resources and their creative use in collaborative learning contexts. Some collaborative web resources are discussion groups and collaboration web 2.0 tools such as wikis and blogs. Webinar is a widely-used tool for organizing online seminars. Distribution lists allow the receipt of regular information through email about events, articles, links based on the theme of the lists to which the user has subscribed. Collaborative groups offer a web space where those interested in a particular topic are able to reflect through thematic forums and share documents. Wikis and blogs are two examples of web 2.0 collaborative tools that offer an intuitive way to create content and shared thoughts on each subject area of interest. Seminars on the web (Webinar) afford the opportunity to participate in real-time seminars on the network and to view them later offline.

1.3. Web Learning Resources

Web resources for learning offer various forms of work with content and activities. An integrated design of learning resources is an important part of the instructional process that helps achieve the expected learning outcomes. Some web learning resources are repositories of educational resources, interactive tutorials, web 2.0 tools (e.g., eBooks, podcasts) and open online courses (OCW, OER, MOOC). Repositories of educational resources offer a variety of teaching materials created by educators, researchers, students, and educational institutions (e.g., Merlot, Agregga) composed of content units with activities and evaluation tests. Interactive tutorials allow one to process guided presentations using text, graphics and audio. Some web 2.0 tools facilitate the use of educational electronic books (eBooks) or audio classes on the Internet [podcast] on the subject that is being addressed, enabling users to create their own productions. OCW (Open Course Ware) ia a source of online courses, offers content resources that have been used in classroom. This type of course is consistent with the OER (Open Educational Resources) initiative to provide freely available educational resources on the Web through Creative Common licenses, a resource for authors wishing to protect their intellectual property. MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) offer the opportunity to update knowledge for teachers in a broad content areas.

1.4. Teaching and Learning with ICT Resources Proposal

As a working proposal for the teacher, we present a conceptual map for teaching and learning with ICT resources, integrating information, collaboration and learning web tools [Figure 3].

Figure 3: Teaching and Learning with ICT Resources (Own elaboration)

ICT resources can be useful for different purposes throughout the teaching-learning process: to visualize concepts (thesaurus), present conceptual background (online encyclopedia), to motivate (videotutorial), etc.

ICT resources can also favor teaching-learning processes at different times: at the beginning, during and at the end of the training sessions.

2. ICT STANDARDS FOR TEACHERS

Several proposals have been made to systematize the levels of acquisition of ICT competences by teachers: ICT-CST UNESCO (2008) or ICT Competencies’ Pentagon (MEN, 2013).

2.1. ICT Competency Standards for Teachers (UNESCO, 2008)

The ICT Competency Framework Standards for Teachers (UNESCO, 2008) offer an opportunity to plan different levels to implement digital teacher competences: Technology literacy, Knowledge Deepening, and Knowledge Creation [Figure 4].

Figure 4: ICT Competency Framework for Teachers (UNESCO, 2008).

This framework is based on previous studies as the International Society for Technology in Education (ISTE) and includes three modules which offer an opportunity to plan different strategies to implement ICT Competences for Teachers:

- *Technology literacy.* Teachers should be able to identify the components of education reform programs that correspond to the policy goals.
- *knowledge deepening.* Teachers should be able to design classroom activities that advance the policy goals.
- *Knowledge creation.* Teachers should be able to develop programs within their school that advance the policy goals.

These three strategies are applied in different modules: (1) understanding ICT in education, (2) curriculum and assessment, (3) pedagogy, (4) ICT, (5) organization and administration, and (6) teacher professional learning. Following this standard, a teacher who wants to develop the “knowledge creation” strategy apply to their “teacher professional learning” will be able, among other competences “to design ICT-based learning resources and environments (...); support students’ continuous reflective learning; and create knowledge communities for student and colleagues” (UNESCO 2011, p.14).

This framework tries to represent the complexity of the educational context including the key components (curriculum, pedagogy, and technology), from different educational perspectives (academic and organizational), offering a framework to introduce educational technology in training institutions. A matrix of 18 different configurations can be adopted by stakeholders. This European proposal has been complemented by researcher initiatives as Churches (2009) who present a selection of web resources to help for the implementation of each configuration of the different modules of the standar.

2.2. ICT Competencies’ Pentagon (MEN, 2013)

The ICT Competences for Professional Teacher Development can be classified in: technological, communicative, pedagogical, management and research (MEN, 2013) [Figure 5].

Figure 5: ICT Competencies’ Pentagon (MEN, 2013)

These competences are developed in different levels or moments of complexity: (1) *exploration* (allows the approach to a set of knowledge that is constituted in the possibility to access states of greater conceptual elaboration), (2) *integration* of knowledge already appropriate for solving problems in different contexts), and (3) *innovation* (emphasis is placed on the exercises of creation, which allows to go beyond the knowledge learned and to imagine new possibilities of action or explanation).

Pedagogical Competence is the ability to use ICT to strengthen teaching and learning processes, recognizing the scope and limitations of incorporating these technologies into the integral training of students and their own professional development. Descriptors of ICT Pedagogical Competence are presented [Table 2].

Table 2: Descriptors of ICT Pedagogical Competence Moments (MEN, 2013)

<i>Explorer</i>	<i>Integrator</i>	<i>Innovator</i>
I use ICT to learn by personal initiative and to update the knowledge and practices of my discipline.	I encourage in my students the autonomous learning and the collaborative learning supported by ICT.	Design ICT-mediated learning environments in accordance with the cognitive, physical, psychological, and social development of my students to promote the development of their competences.
I identify educational problems in my teaching practice and the opportunities, implications and risks of using ICT to attend them.	I use ICT with my students to meet their needs and interests and propose solutions to learning problems.	I propose ICT-mediated educational projects that allow reflection on one's own learning and knowledge production.
I know a variety of strategies and methodologies supported by ICT, to plan and follow up on my teaching work.	Implementing didactic strategies mediated by ICT, to strengthen in my students learning to solve real-life problems.	I evaluate the results obtained with the implementation of strategies that make use of ICT and promote a culture of monitoring, feedback and permanent improvement.

Each competence can be developed independently, which implies that a teacher can be in different moments of development in each one of these competences and the pentagon allows to identify his profile and offers guidelines for designing and implementing professional development programs for teachers. The guidelines are designed to recognize the individual or collective needs, formulate interventions aligned with the principles presented and follow the professional development processes to achieve the objectives.

3. TECHNO-PEDAGOGICAL MODELS

Teachers have at their disposal some techno-pedagogical models for the curricular integration of technology in the classroom, like for example: TPACK (Mishra & Koehler, 2006) or SAMR (Puentedura, 2014).

3.1. TPCK Model

The TPCK model focuses on the importance of knowledge (K) in Content (C), Pedagogy (P) and Technology (T) and the possible relationships between them [Figure 6].

Figure 6: TPACK Model (Mishra & Koehler, 2006)

This model allows us to incorporate resources among different types of knowledge involved in the design of digital educational resources: content, pedagogy and technology. Some exemplifications are presented integrating the model during the design process of resources.

- Tools to improve the presentation of content, such as graphic editors, publishers and multimedia (TK-technological knowledge).
- Tools to facilitate reflection on learning can be blogs or social forums (PK-pedagogical knowledge).
- Resources for further knowledge of the subject area can be online databases and online encyclopedias (e.g., Wikipedia, WikiEducator) (CK-content knowledge).

Each situation requires from teachers a combination of these factors, there is no single solution or standard practice for all teachers. Each type of knowledge included in the TPACK model and their interrelationships is described by Mishra and Koehler (2006), and Koehler and Mishra (2009) (Table 3).

Table 3: TPACK model types of knowledge (Based on Mishra & Koehler 2006, and Koehler & Mishra, 2009)

Type of Knowledge	Description
CK-Content knowledge	Teacher knowledge on curriculum content (concepts, theories, ideas, organizational frameworks, etc.) at different stages or modalities. Teachers must master and understand the depth of foundations of knowledge of the disciplines to teach their subjects.
PK- Pedagogical knowledge	Teacher knowledge about the variety of teaching and learning methods, teaching strategies, dynamics, practices or activities that allow interaction and collaboration by students. In this kind of knowledge is taken into account the styles of teaching and learning, classroom management, planning of teaching units, student assessment, etc. Includes objectives, development of key competencies and application of methodological strategies. The teacher tries to understand how students learn, leading classroom management skills, planning and student assessment.
TK-Technology knowledge	Teacher knowledge about traditional and ICT-based technologies that can be integrated into the curriculum, and the importance of its permanent update for an educational use. It implies a fluidity and management of technologies that go beyond computer literacy. Teachers are required to have a mastery of technology to apply it productively for information processing, communication and problem solving.
PCK-Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Teacher knowledge about pedagogy applied to the teaching content of a specific knowledge area. Professor finds many ways to represent the contents and adapting educational materials based on prior knowledge, interests, and abilities of students.
TCK-Technological Content Knowledge	Teacher knowledge to understand which technologies are best suited for a learning content. At the same time, the type of content requires technological changes to curriculum integration.
TPK-Technological Pedagogical Knowledge	Teacher knowledge to understand how the teaching-learning process can change when a technology resource with a teaching strategy is used.
TPACK-Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Teacher knowledge to implement teaching strategies appropriate to the specific context. It refers to effective teaching and learning through technology to facilitate learning based on the characteristics of students and context.

The different types of knowledge of the TPACK model (TK, CK, PK, TCK, PCK, TPK, TPACK) can be to be applied to specific educational purposes and contexts. This model has been applied to know the level of competence on ICT by teachers and to propose a pathway to their professional training process.

The challenge lies in the ability to integrate knowledge of the three elements -technology, pedagogy and content knowledge - depending on the variables in each educational setting.

3.2. SAMR (Puentedura, 2014)

The SAMR Model by Puentedura (2014) offers different levels of the role of technology, from *enhancement* (substitution and augmentation) to *transformation* (modification and redefinition) [Figure 7].

Figure 7: SAMR Model (Puentedura, 2014)

Following Puentedura (2014) the use of technology in education goes through different levels in an increasing order: substitution, increase, modification and redefinition. These levels can be characterized in terms of the role of technology as follow:

- *Substitution*. The technology acts as a substitute, a direct tool with no functional change.
- *Augmentation*. The technology acts as a direct replacement with a functional improvement.
- *Modification*. The technology allows an important task redesign.
- *Redefinition*. The technology allows the creation of new tasks, previously inconceivable.

SAMR Model offers an itinerary of continuous ICT training of teachers from basic to advanced levels: (1) ICT <without> functional change; (2) ICT <with> functional change; (3) ICT <with> redesigned activities; and (4) ICT <with> new activities.

The SAMR proposal contributes to understand the *Technology* concept, defined by his author as the beliefs about how technology can and should be used in teaching practices. This model has inspired other researchers as Roberts (2013) who propose for novel teachers to focus more on the role of teachers and students than in tasks. To do this, it proposes the following steps: *traditional* (traditional pedagogy with technology support), *enhanced* (integration of multiple tools to create an enhanced learning experience), *choice* (selected tasks using a specified range of tools) and *handoff* (flexible choice of tools to achieve an authentic product from the students' interests. In this same line are expressed McKnight, O'Malley, Ruzic, Horsley, Franey & Bassett (2016) identifying different roles that technology plays in enhancing teaching and learning: Access, Communication and Feedback, Teacher Time, Student Work.

4. RESOURCES IN A B-LEARNING DISTANCE EDUCATION CONTEXT: UNED CASE STUDY

Teachers should integrate traditional and ICT resources to take advantage of institutional media and services and at the same time to take advantage of the favorable environment in which students are digital natives. We describe the resources used in a b-Learning distance education context.

Teachers who develop their subjects in distance learning contexts can create conceptual epistemological frameworks for her subject, in which the students can learn within a complementary set of educational resources. The UNED methodology is based on b-Learning modality, combining face-to-face tutorship in training centers, traditional media (print, audiovisual, etc.), web tools (LMS, webconference, etc.) and in-person exams [Figure 8].

Figure 8: Resources in a b-Learning Distance Education Context (Own elaboration)

The b-Learning system at the UNED use an own LMS platform (aLF) in which occurs the different types of interaction among students, teachers and tutors. Institutional resources are available to complement the platform: documents repository (eSpacio), video lessons (Canal UNED), ebooks (ebrary, linceo+), etc. In addition to the digital components, students have traditional media at their disposal as the study guide and the basic text book. We present the results of several studies carried out with undergraduate and graduate students of the School of Education at the UNED.

Posgraduates students who answer to a questionnaire on the use of the training platform (n=115) say they use *quite* and *a lot* (62.6%) classic materials (books, articles, ...) in addition to the training platform. Appropriate use of the training platform “*opens a new world of opportunities both classroom training, and distance. It also contributes to the new teaching models to promote active student participation in their training*”. [Student_27]. A disadvantage in the use of the platform is “*Too much informative noise in the forum messages*”. [Student_43].

Graduate students of Education School at UNED who answer to a questionnaire on the ICT Competence as users and creators (n=49) believe that have a *high* and *advanced* ICT competence as user (48,3%), however they consider that have a *low* and *medium* as creator (75,9%). Among the advantages provided as a user of technological resources in the training process are: “*the speed with which I can obtain information on any subject, the ease of developing training and the possibility of conducting training courses (formal education / non-formal education) Through an online platform*” [Student_14]. The main advantage as a creator is “*that when you create a tool you adapt it to the use you want to give it*” [Student_13]. Among the difficulties identified as users and as creators highlights that “*not all sources are reliables*” [Student_14 & Student_5].

CONCLUSIONS

Teachers need to acquire skills that allow integration of web resources for information, collaboration and learning purposes. For Bates (2015), many media are better than one, because “this allows learners with different preferences for learning to be accommodated and to allow subject matter to be taught in different ways through different media” (p. 206). In this line of recommendations, Adams et al (2017) consider that «Educators are increasingly expected to employ a variety of technology based tools, such as digital learning resources and courseware, and engage in online discussions and collaborative authoring” (p. 23).

Teachers have standards in ICT skills developed by institutions at an international level to deal with the planning of teaching sequences, which can be enriched with the institutional repositories of resources developed by both designers and teachers, and Taxonomies of criteria to evaluate the technological and pedagogical quality of web resources. The innovation in teaching needs in-depth knowledge of media design to make the appropriate and creative decisions to select and apply ICT resources and virtual scenarios to solve the most important challenges in the training process (Medina & Domínguez, 2015).

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU-UNESCO, 2014) analysis presents different stages to introduce ICT in education depending on the penetration level in education: *e-readiness* (trained teachers through basic ICT infrastructure), *e-intensity* (ICT-enhanced content development and innovative pedagogy management through distance education resources), and *e-impact* (ICT for lifelong learning through podcasting, videoconferencing, etc. resources). This ICT integration requires following Hibbitts & Travin (2015) a combination of a stablish sequence of steps from Learning and Technology point of view: Assess learners needs, Define and Conceptualize, Assess technology fit, Design, Evaluate, Implement and Deliver.

Digital Teacher Competence requires: (1) to know the available resource repositories to respond the specific educational needs, (2) to apply technological and pedagogical models that provide a framework for the integration of ICT in educational contexts, (3) to evaluate the adequacy of didactic strategies with ICT through exemplifications.

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- TPACK. Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge Model [website] <http://www.tpack.org/>
- UNED. Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia [*Spanish National University of Distance Education*] [website] <http://www.uned.es/>

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